

Performance comparison of MySQL and PostgreSQL

Thanh Cong Nguyen

Abstract

Micro-services architecture is becoming an increasingly popular choice for e-commerce systems to handle global-scaled transactions due to its ability to independently scale only the heavy-traffic services, thus improving performance while reducing server costs. Additionally, a stateless architecture is employed to further enhance the scalability of each individual service. While a stateless application does not store session-specific state within the application itself, the data stored and managed in a database is fundamental to its functioning. Thus, database performance is crucial for computer scientists in engineering stateless applications, especially since its performance cannot be improved with application code optimization. This technical report presents a performance comparison between two popular relational database management systems: MySQL and PostgreSQL.

1. Introduction

Relational database management systems are essential components of modern software applications, providing a structured and efficient means of storing, managing, and retrieving data. As database performance plays an important role in the responsiveness and scalability of software applications, various database solutions have been developed.

Thus, it is beneficial for software architects to know the performance characteristics of

available database solutions, as once a solution is chosen, it will be difficult to switch to a different one. MySQL and PostgreSQL are two open-source relational database management systems that are widely used in web applications and other software.

The primary objective of this technical report is to assess and evaluate the performance of MySQL and PostgreSQL across various benchmark scenarios. In the following sections of this research, I will outline the

benchmarking methodology and present the benchmark results.

2. Methodology

The performance measurement was carried out using the following methodology:

- Objective: Measure execution times for running SQL scripts in MySQL and PostgreSQL.
- SQL scripts: There are 8 tests covering INSERT/SELECT/UPDATE/DELETE with or without an INDEX.
- Setup: The SQL scripts were executed on PostgreSQL 15 and MySQL 8 running on a MacBook Pro 2019 with a 2.6 GHz 6-Core Intel Core i7 processor and 16 GB of 2400 MHz DDR4 RAM.
- Data collection: Execute the same SQL scripts on both MySQL and PostgreSQL and measure the execution time for each test.

3. Results

3.1 1000 INSERTs

PostgreSQL script execution was 166% faster than MySQL's when inserting 1000 rows into a table. When inserting data into a table using

indexing, PostgreSQL still proved to be 125% faster than MySQL.

Figure 1: 1000 INSERTs - MySQL

```

mysql> CREATE TABLE test1 (a INTEGER, b INTEGER, c INTEGER);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (1,1,1);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (2,2,2);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (3,3,3);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (4,4,4);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (5,5,5);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (6,6,6);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (7,7,7);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (8,8,8);
mysql> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (9,9,9);
  
```

Name	Value
Queries	1001
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	757
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	757
Start time	2023-07-07 21:10:52.471
Finish time	2023-07-07 21:10:53.433

Figure 2: 1000 INSERTs - PostgreSQL

```

postgres> CREATE TABLE test1 (a INTEGER, b INTEGER, c INTEGER);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (1,1,1);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (2,2,2);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (3,3,3);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (4,4,4);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (5,5,5);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (6,6,6);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (7,7,7);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (8,8,8);
postgres> INSERT INTO test1 VALUES (9,9,9);
  
```

Name	Value
Queries	1001
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	285
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	285
Start time	2023-07-07 21:13:16.774
Finish time	2023-07-07 21:13:17.201

Figure 3: 1000 INSERTs in indexed table - MySQL

```

mysql> CREATE TABLE test2 (a INTEGER, b INTEGER, c INTEGER);
mysql> CREATE INDEX index2 ON test2(c);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (1,1,1);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (2,2,2);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (3,3,3);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (4,4,4);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (5,5,5);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (6,6,6);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (7,7,7);
mysql> INSERT INTO test2 VALUES (8,8,8);
  
```

Name	Value
Queries	1002
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	1056
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	1056
Start time	2023-07-07 20:08:21.094
Finish time	2023-07-07 20:08:22.479

Figure 4: 1000 INSERTs in indexed table - PostgreSQL

Figure 7: 1000 SELECTs in indexed table - MySQL

3.2. 1000 SELECTs

Similar to INSERT statements, for SELECT statements, PostgreSQL also performed better than MySQL, being 98% and 21% faster without and with an index, respectively.

Figure 5: 1000 SELECTs - MySQL

Figure 6: 1000 SELECTs - PostgreSQL

Figure 8: 1000 SELECTs in indexed table - PostgreSQL

3.3. 1000 UPDATES

Again, when executing UPDATE statements, PostgreSQL outperformed MySQL by 229% in the non-indexed table test and 101% in the indexed table test.

Figure 9: 1000 UPDATES - MySQL

Figure 10: 1000 UPDATES - PostgreSQL

```

<postgres> test5_postgres >
UPDATE test1 SET b = 999 WHERE c = 1;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 998 WHERE c = 2;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 997 WHERE c = 3;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 996 WHERE c = 4;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 995 WHERE c = 5;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 994 WHERE c = 6;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 993 WHERE c = 7;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 992 WHERE c = 8;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 991 WHERE c = 9;
UPDATE test1 SET b = 990 WHERE c = 10;

```

Name	Value
Queries	1000
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	450
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	450
Start time	2023-07-08 22:16:31.535
Finish time	2023-07-08 22:16:32.173

Figure 11: 1000 UPDATES in indexed table - MySQL

```

<mysql> test6_mysql >
UPDATE test2 SET b = 999 WHERE c = 1;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 998 WHERE c = 2;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 997 WHERE c = 3;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 996 WHERE c = 4;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 995 WHERE c = 5;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 994 WHERE c = 6;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 993 WHERE c = 7;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 992 WHERE c = 8;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 991 WHERE c = 9;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 990 WHERE c = 10;

```

Name	Value
Queries	1000
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	683
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	683
Start time	2023-07-08 22:30:45.734
Finish time	2023-07-08 22:30:46.554

Figure 12: 1000 UPDATES in indexed table - PostgreSQL

```

<postgres> test6_postgres >
UPDATE test2 SET b = 999 WHERE c = 1;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 998 WHERE c = 2;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 997 WHERE c = 3;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 996 WHERE c = 4;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 995 WHERE c = 5;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 994 WHERE c = 6;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 993 WHERE c = 7;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 992 WHERE c = 8;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 991 WHERE c = 9;
UPDATE test2 SET b = 990 WHERE c = 10;

```

Name	Value
Queries	1000
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	340
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	340
Start time	2023-07-08 22:29:03.407
Finish time	2023-07-08 22:29:03.895

3.4. 1000 DELETES

Finally, for DELETE statements, consistent with the previous tests, PostgreSQL also outperformed MySQL by 224% in the non-indexed table test and 197% in the indexed table test.

Figure 13: 1000 DELETES - MySQL

```

<mysql> test7_mysql >
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 1;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 2;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 3;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 4;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 5;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 6;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 7;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 8;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 9;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 10;

```

Name	Value
Queries	1000
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	950
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	950
Start time	2023-07-08 22:39:42.307
Finish time	2023-07-08 22:39:43.379

Figure 14: 1000 DELETES - PostgreSQL

```

<postgres> test7_postgres >
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 1;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 2;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 3;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 4;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 5;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 6;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 7;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 8;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 9;
DELETE FROM test1 WHERE c = 10;

```

Name	Value
Queries	1000
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	293
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	293
Start time	2023-07-08 22:37:33.340
Finish time	2023-07-08 22:37:33.751

Figure 15: 1000 DELETES in indexed table - MySQL

The screenshot shows a MySQL terminal window with the following content:

```
<mysql> test8_mysql ×  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 1;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 2;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 3;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 4;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 5;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 6;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 7;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 8;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 9;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 10;
```

Below the commands is a 'Statistics 1' window with the following data:

Name	Value
Queries	1000
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	758
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	758
Start time	2023-07-08 22:48:40.235
Finish time	2023-07-08 22:48:41.115

Figure 16: 1000 DELETES in indexed table - PostgreSQL

The screenshot shows a PostgreSQL terminal window with the following content:

```
<postgres> test8_postgres ×  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 1;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 2;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 3;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 4;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 5;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 6;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 7;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 8;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 9;  
DELETE FROM test2 WHERE c = 10;
```

Below the commands is a 'Statistics 1' window with the following data:

Name	Value
Queries	1000
Updated Rows	1000
Execute time (ms)	255
Fetch time (ms)	0
Total time (ms)	255
Start time	2023-07-08 22:44:44.630
Finish time	2023-07-08 22:44:45.012

4. Summary

Several tests were conducted to assess how PostgreSQL 15 and MySQL 8 perform on a macOS system. Based on these experiments, the following overall findings were derived:

- PostgreSQL outperformed MySQL in all tests.
- This performance advantage reduced on an indexed table.

The results provided here should be considered with the following cautionary notes:

- These tests were not designed to evaluate the performance of multiple users, joins, and subqueries
- The tests were conducted on a comparatively small database containing 1000 rows. They do not provide an assessment of how effectively the database engines handle larger-scale problems.